

A Study in the EP Activity Evaluation of certain 1,2,4-Triazoles in the Four Ball Test†

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The potential extreme pressure activity of certain 3-mercapto-4-aryl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazoles in paraffin oil has been evaluated with reference to a commercial S-P containing additive on a four-ball machine. 3-Mercapto-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazole showing lower values of wear-scar diameter (0.60 mm) and friction coefficient (0.018) at ISL (80 kgf) and higher values of 2.5 second SDL, (90 kgf), weld load (224 kgf), mean Hertz load (41 kgf) and flash temperature parameter (244), was found to be best. This was corroborated and confirmed by the study of the surface topography and surface chemistry of wear-scar matrix by scanning electron microscopy and Auger electron spectroscopy techniques respectively.

The prime function of a lubricant is to separate the metallic surfaces by forming a lubricating layer between them. However, due to rapid strides in the industrialisation and advancement in the areas of engineering design and technology, more and more sophisticated machines are being used and sometimes these run in a very arduous conditions. Under these conditions the mineral oils only are often unable to provide satisfactory lubrication, resulting in catastrophic wear, pitting, scuffing or scoring of the rubbing components. These casualties may be minimised by the addition of an appropriate additive to the mineral oils.

These EP additives increase the load carrying capacity of the mineral oil and reduce power loss and fuel consumption by reducing frictional resistance.

In view of the extensive applications of EP additives in hypoid gears and metal cutting operations¹ and our continued efforts in the development of better temperature-resistant nitrogen and sulphur heterocyclic compounds², this paper reports the preparation and evaluation of some 1,2,4-triazoles (1a—d) as potentially active EP additives in the four-ball test with paraffin oil as a base fluid and 12.7 mm diameter alloy steel bearing balls as specimen. The surface analysis was carried out by scanning electron microscopy and Auger electron spectroscopy techniques.

Results and Discussion

Four ball wear and friction test data are tabulated in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows the relationship between log wear scar diameter and log load for paraffin oil without and with reference additive and 3-mercapto-4-aryl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazoles. The wear-load diagram (Fig. 1) shows two different regions—the region before initial seizure (where there is a sudden increase in the

measured wear scar diameter) is termed as the antiwear (AW) region and the region after initial seizure, where the wear scars are larger, is termed as the extreme pressure (EP) region. The wear-load diagram for compound 1d shows that the curve deviates from Hertz line at a load of 80 kgf and finally welding occurs at a load of 224 kgf. It is clear from Table 1 that all the additives definitely give higher ISLs, 2.5 SDLs and final WLs as compared to the plain paraffin oil and provide higher WSD values in comparison to the reference additive.

Fig. 1. Plots of log load vs log wear scar diameter: (x) paraffin oil without additive, and with (O) 1a, (Δ) 1b, (●) 1c, (▲) 1d, (□) reference additive.

Fig. 2 depicts the relationship between mean specific pressure (pm) and applied load. The shapes of the curves are similar. The pm at contact points decreases sharply upto 2.5 SDL, then remains more or less constant.

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TABLE 1—RESULTS OBTAINED WITH DIFFERENT 1,2,4-TRIAZOLES IN PARAFFIN OIL USED AS EP ADDITIVE

Sl. no.	Lubricant +Compound	Initial seizure load (ISL) kgf	Observation at ISL			2.5 second seizure delay kgf	Observation at just before weld load			Weld load (WL) kgf	Flash temperature parameter (FTP) max	Mean Hertz load (MHL) kgf	Pressure wear index (PWI)	
			d^* mm	μ^*	p_m^* kg mm ⁻²		Load kgf	d^* mm	μ^*					p_m^* kg mm ⁻²
1.	Paraffin oil (without additive)	56	2.05	0.022	6.93	63	100	2.73	0.43	6.98	112	25	11	4
2.	Paraffin oil+1a	72	0.72	0.020	72.22	80	200	2.25	0.15	20.54	224	129	33	6
3.	Paraffin oil+1b	72	0.65	0.027	88.62	80	156	2.10	0.11	18.39	178	132	29	5
4.	Paraffin oil+1c	80	0.63	0.018	103.82	90	178	2.03	0.16	22.46	200	171	38	6
5.	Paraffin oil+1d	80	0.60	0.018	115.56	90	200	2.10	0.11	23.58	224	244	41	8
6.	Paraffin oil+Reference additive	112	0.68	0.066	137.85	126	156	2.12	0.16	18.05	178	256	55	7

d^* = Mean wear scar diameter ; μ^* = friction coefficient ; p_m^* = Mean specific pressure at contact points.

The chemical film formed by metal-additive interaction fails above a pressure of 23.58 kg mm⁻² on the contact area in case of 3-mercapto-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazole. Other additives appear to form films which are stable at pressure lower than 22.46 kg mm⁻² (Table 1).

and sulphur heterocyclic compounds enhance the activity of the additives.

Compounds 1d and 1c indicate comparatively higher values of FTP (244 and 171), MHL (41 kgf and 38 kgf) and PWI (8 and 6) respectively indicating their potential applicability as EP additives.

Fig. 2. Load vs mean specific pressure at contact points : (x) paraffin oil without additive, and with (O) 1a, (Δ) 1b, (●) 1c, (▲) 1d, (□) reference additive.

Fig. 3 shows plots between friction coefficient (μ) values and applied loads. The additive admixtures with paraffin oil show roughly similar curves. The plain paraffin oil fails at lower load. However, the additives 1d and 1c give lower values of μ (0.018, 0.018 and 0.11, 0.16) at ISLs and just before WLs respectively, thereby indicating a general decreasing trend in the μ values upto WLs. This appears to be due to the slow decomposition of additives at certain range of temperatures and pressures, when the additive interacts with metal surface to form a mixed film of iron sulphide-iron chloride-iron oxide, which functions satisfactorily up to the WL.

It appears that chlorine or oxygen present as additional elements besides sulphur in the nitrogen

Fig. 3. Load vs friction coefficient : (x) paraffin oil without additive, and with (O) 1a, (Δ) 1b, (●) 1c, (▲) 1d, (□) reference additive.

Surface analysis :

SEM : To reveal the topography of the scars produced, the technique of SEM (scanning electron microscopy) was used. The loads selected were at 2.5 SDL (90 kgf) and just before WL (200 kgf) for the additive which was found to be effective. Stains of sludge or oil found to be on the ball surface in the vicinity of the wear scar were then cleaned with acetone in an ultrasonic bath. The flow pattern at the leading edge indicates that the lubricant flowed from left to right.

Fig. 4. Scanning electron micrographs of wear scar surface produced with paraffin oil + compound 1d ; magnification (a) 30X, 90 kgf, (b) 30X, 200 kgf, (c) 200X, 90 kgf and (d) 200X, 200 kgf.

Micrographs of the wear scars produced after 60 second tests are shown in Fig. 4 for the additive 1d. Adhesive type of wear appears to take place incorporating the transfer of one material onto the other. This may be due to the junction growth and subsequent rupture. All the scars are regular in shape (Figs. 4a and b). The additive 1d appears to be potentially attractive as it provides smoother surface even at high loads as compared to the paraffin oil alone and its admixture with reference additive. The additive proves to be an effective EP additive.

AES: The wear scar surface obtained by using additive 1d on bearing ball at 90 kgf (2.5 SDL) was analysed employing a scanning Auger Microprobe with a primary electron beam voltage of 3 keV, a current of ~ 10 nA and a beam diameter of < 7000 Å. The Auger spectrum (Fig. 5) confirmed

the presence of Fe, O, C, Cl and S as the load bearing elements.

Conclusion: Among the 3-mercapto-4-aryl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazoles studied, 3-mercapto-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazole appears to be a good extreme pressure lubrication additive on the basis of the values of the various parameters determined.

Experimental

The additives, 3-mercapto-4-aryl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazoles (1)^a were prepared by cyclising *N*-isonicotinyl-*N'*-arylthiosemicarbazides (2)⁴ with 2*N* NaOH solution: 1a (42%), m.p. 275° (Found: C, 61.39; H, 3.89; N, 22.00. C₁₈H₁₀N₄S calcd. for: C, 61.52; H, 3.94; N, 22.05%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1560 cm⁻¹ (C=N conjugated); ¹H nmr δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 8.4–8.8 (m, pyridine-H), 7.4–7.7 (m,

Fig. 5. AES of compound 1d at 90 kgf load.

ArH) and 1.5–1.8 (SH, exchangeable with deuterium); 1b (46%), 248°; ν_{\max} 1 590 cm^{-1} (C=N conjugated); 1c (43%), 235°; ν_{\max} 1 570 cm^{-1} (C=N conjugated); 1d (44%), 265°; ν_{\max} 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N conjugated).

1a ; Ar = Phenyl
1b ; Ar = *p*-Methylphenyl

1c ; Ar = *p*-Methoxyphenyl
1d ; Ar = *p*-Chlorophenyl

Alloy steel bearing balls (12.7 mm dia.) composition ; C 0.53, Cr 0.48 ; Mn 0.58% ; hardness 628 VHN) were used. The base fluid was paraffin oil : specific gravity 0.82 at 26° ; viscosity, 128 cP at 26° and 5.34 cP at 100° ; cloud point, -2° ; pour point, -8° ; flash point, 180° ; fire point, 200°. A sulphur-phosphorous commercially available reference additive having the following properties was used ; S 29.5–33.5 P 1.5–2.0% ; specific gravity at 26°, 0.999 ; and viscosity at 26°, 267 cP.

Testing machine : A four-ball EP lubricant testing machine was used for the evaluation of the different additives. In the machine, a vertical spindle rotated a chuck at a speed of 1475 rpm, equivalent to a sliding speed of 567 mm s^{-1} . Four new balls were employed for each test. The duration of a test was 60 s and different loads were applied on the lower three balls to press against the top ball. Series of tests were performed until the weld load was reached with various additives.

The synthesised additives and reference additive (0.5% wt/vol) were dissolved in paraffin oil and the mixture was homogenised at 60° with continuous stirring for 30 min. To evaluate the EP activity of the different additives the various parameters were determined (Table 1) by standard method*.

Scanning electron microscope and Auger electron spectroscope were used for surface analysis.

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